

College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka

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**30th Annual Academic Sessions of the
College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka**

***Best Practices in Public
Health***

Abstracts of Oral and Poster Presentations

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The College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka (CCPSL) is the oldest and the first medical professional body which has been established under an Act of Parliament for public health professionals in Sri Lanka. The Annual Academic Sessions of the CCPSL is the largest gathering of Public Health physicians in the country.

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Editorial Office:

Journal of the College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka
No. 6
'Wijerama House'
Wijerama Mawatha
Colombo 7
Sri Lanka.

Phone: 0094(0)114487139

Fax: 0094(0)114487139

E-mail: editorjccpsl@gmail.com

Collaborations and innovative approach of initiative Non-communicable Disease Week program at Colombo Regional Director of Health Services (RDHS) area, Sri Lanka

Maduranga M.A.V.A.¹, Karunatilaka M.N.¹, Perera M.N.S.², Srimali M.A.C.³, Kumari W.P.L.D.⁴, Shashika W.S.⁵, Madumali K.K.I.⁶

¹Office of Regional Director of Health Services, Colombo, Sri Lanka; ²PMCU Pannipitiya, Sri Lanka; ³PMCU Sedawatta, Sri Lanka; ⁴PMCU Rukmalgama, Sri Lanka; ⁵PMCU Boralesgamuwa, Sri Lanka; ⁶PMCU Fork Art Center, Battaramulla, Sri Lanka

Background: Non-communicable diseases (NCDs) pose a major public health burden in Sri Lanka. NCDs account for about 83% of annual deaths in the country. A special week-long NCD screening week by Colombo RDHS targeted adults 35+ and high-risk groups

Description of the initiative: A stakeholder mapping was done. Stakeholders included curative institutions, preventive institutions, non-health government and private institutions as well as community-based organizations. Discussions were held with each of these stakeholders and the expected contributions without disrupting their routine services were agreed upon.

Methods used for evaluation: The number of stakeholders involved in the NCD week and the qualitative analysis of the level of collaboration.

Results: District-level coordinated screening events were conducted at high-traffic sites including markets, religious places, government offices, universities, and transport hubs. A mobile medical unit, provided by a local bank, facilitated outreach. Private sector partners assisted with logistics. Community-based organizations helped in dissemination of the messages to the public on the NCD week and on the venues of the screening. In contrast to the district's previous quarterly average of 9,709 screenings, over 3,500 screenings were conducted within just one week and high-risk individuals were referred to relevant clinics

Lessons learnt: The initiative emphasized the importance of early planning, strong intersectoral collaboration, and adaptability in implementing large-scale health programs. Public-private partnerships and innovations like mobile medical units helped maintain services despite logistical hurdles. Persistent issues with staffing, transport, and equipment highlighted the further opportunities for improvement.

Key words: Non-Communicable diseases, Integrated health services, Community-based screening, Preventive health care, Colombo RDHS, Healthy Lifestyle Clinics, Intersectoral Collaboration

Corresponding author email: muthash@ymail.com